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**COMPARING TRADITIONAL AND NON-TRADITIONAL METHODS
IN TERMS OF IMPROVING EFFECTIVENESS IN TEACHING
ENGLISH**

***Abstract.** As teaching and learning strategies and styles are changing due to the advancements of technology, using only traditional methods seems to be less effective than using both traditional and non-traditional ones. This article is dedicated to comparing different methods according to learner's level and using a wide range of methods in the classroom to improve English proficiency.*

***Keywords:** GTM, SLA, EFL, TPR, Direct method, English environment, time-management, student-centered lessons.*

Introduction

In teaching process, different educators apply diverse methods taking students' level, needs and preference into consideration. I will give explanations of various methods with examples.

Traditional Methods:

- Grammar Translation Method (GTM): This method is about learning grammar rules and translating sentences between any foreign or second language and the native language. It emphasizes reading and writing skills more rather than speaking and listening.

- Direct Method: This method focuses on oral communication and immersion in the target language. It emphasizes teaching vocabulary, phrases, and idioms through demonstration and conversation.

- Audio-Lingual Method: This method involves drills, repetition, and memorization to develop listening and speaking skills. It focuses on teaching patterns of sounds, sentence structures, and intonation.

Non-Traditional Methods:

- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): This approach emphasizes developing communicative competence in the target language through real-life situations. It motivates students to interact with each other using the target language.

- Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): In this non-traditional method, students are distributed specific tasks or activities to complete using the target language. The focus is on practical application of language skills rather than rote memorization.

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- Content-Based Instruction (CBI): CBI integrates language learning with subject matter content. Students learn the target language while studying a particular topic or subject of interest.

Effectiveness Comparison:

1. Traditional methods prioritize accuracy over fluency while non-traditional methods focus more on improving communicative competence.

2. Traditional methods often rely heavily on explicit grammar instructions, which can be overwhelming for most learners. Non-traditional methods provide students with opportunities for authentic language use without excessive emphasis on grammar rules.

3. Non-traditional methods promote active engagement in effective tasks or activities enabling learners to experience the practical use of the language in real-life situations.

4. Traditional methods may be more appropriate for learners who want to acquire language learning structure and clear guidelines, while non-traditional methods are often favored by those whose creativity and autonomy are dominant in their learning process.

Literature review

While analyzing different sources to differentiate traditional and non-traditional methods and the effectiveness of using them for both educators and language learners. The traditional learning environment has established a prevailing type of the educational process in higher educational establishments for many years. Over about the last 10 years, computer-based learning has considerably revolutionized and revitalized the university sector, becoming an icon of this cutting-edge era higher education provision (Selwyn, 2007). The primary reason has been the possibilities for technologies to end up with possible and productive opportunities regarding communication, interaction, and collaboration (Harasim et al., 1995).

In terms of knowledge and skills for innovative and complex problem solving within multicultural and multidisciplinary environments, they can be acquired through non-traditional learning methods which are of a wide-concept of learning through problem solving, and collaborative and virtual learning. Collaborative learning has been found to significantly improve the learning process and student participation (Benbunan-Fich and Hiltz, 2003). Additionally, studies show that collaborative learning results in higher achievement and getting more information than competitive or individual learning (Hooper & Hannafin, 1988; Johnson & Johnson, 1996).

According to Meyer, 2003, virtual discussion and information sharing can be considered as slow because non-native students might encounter difficulties when communicating in a foreign language including English or Russian. Therefore, it is fundamentally important that students might express their ideas, thoughts or explanations very clearly using short sentences. And also, using technology can cause some problems for students with poor IT equipment, faulty

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electronic supply or inadequate internet services (Morse, 2003) because they cannot follow virtual discussions or chats consistently. Individuals also need some amount of time to acquire target language and build their confidence when working with online tools in order to become efficient and effective (Scantlebury, 2009) and become familiar with the useful functions offered by online tools.

In conclusion, both traditional and non-traditional methods have their advantages and disadvantages when it comes to improving language acquisition. The choice of method depends on individual learner preferences, goals, and the specific context of language learning. As we are living in the technology period and globalized world, we need to know about different techniques, activities and methods. Teachers in many cases use various methods namely traditional and non-traditional methods at the same time in order not to make students dissatisfied or bored with out lessons. This article that there are certain similarities and several differences regarding various non-traditional learning methods, based on the students' opinions and preferences. In both educators the students prefer non-traditional learning methods` in language acquisition. The majority of the students think that any knowledge can be obtained this way would be more holistic and sustainable. They sometimes claim that any disagreements occur at the task or problem-solving stage, where students are dissatisfied with the teaching methods chosen or techniques that educators base on in the lessons. It is important to point out that non-traditional learning methods often require a full commitment by all group members. The success of a learning process is based on teachers' personal choice of different methods according to levels and preferences of the target group.

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